

Choosing the Right Test Generation Tool: A Guide for Software Practitioners

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Abstract: **Context:** As software systems become increasingly complex, testing automation plays a critical role in ensuring product quality and reliability. However, the wide variety of available test generation tools with distinct purposes, features, and approaches makes it difficult for practitioners to select the most appropriate option for their projects. **Goal:** This study aims to identify, analyze, and compare test generation tools reported in both academic and industrial contexts, providing a practical reference guide to support software professionals in tool selection decisions. **Method:** We conducted a Multivocal Literature Review (MLR) complemented by a two-round survey with 87 software practitioners. The MLR identified tools and features reported in white and grey literature, while the survey assessed practitioners' familiarity, usage, and perceptions of advantages and challenges associated with these tools. **Results:** The findings reveal a persistent gap between academic proposals and industrial adoption. While tools such as Postman, Selenium, and Cypress are among the most widely used tools in practice, academic tools like Monkey and Dynodroid remain rarely adopted. Practitioners value visibility, integration, and traceability as key features, whereas inconsistency and maintenance effort are seen as primary challenges. **Conclusions:** The study contributes a structured reference guide to assist professionals in selecting tools suitable for specific testing contexts. It also provides insights for researchers aiming to align future tool development with industry needs, fostering better usability, integration, and sustainability of automated testing solutions.

Keywords: Software Testing, Software Testing Tools, Test Generation Tools, Tools Comparison, Multivocal Literature Review

Categories: D.2.2, D.2.3, D.2.5

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1 Introduction

The software testing process plays an important role in achieving and assessing the quality of a software product. Software testing requires the creation of effective test cases that target potential bug-prone areas, a process that is time-consuming and labor-intensive when done manually [Tachiyama et al., 2017]. Adopting automatic test case generation tools proves beneficial to improve the efficiency of test cases and, consequently, the entire testing process. In this context, efficiency refers to the ability of test cases to achieve high defect detection, code or functionality coverage, and reduced execution time, while minimizing manual effort and redundancy. Such tools expedite and simplify testing procedures, thereby optimizing the overall testing workflow [Tachiyama et al., 2017].

In order to offer more effective and secure alternatives, a software project can employ a testing tool. However, due to the diverse array of available tools, each offering distinct approaches, each one with inherent advantages and disadvantages in their execution [Naik & Tripathy, 2011], the decision of which tool to use can be challenging. This decision entails a cost-benefit analysis and a bad decision may lead to an inappropriate allocation of project resources, potentially resulting in losses for the organization. Understanding specific project requirements and identifying the most suitable test generation tools for software development teams is crucial. This understanding empowers the professionals responsible for conducting tests to ensure the quality and seamless functionality of the software. It also ensures efficient utilization of resources dedicated to testing [Corradini et al., 2021].

Given this context, this work aims to **investigate the test generation tools used in academia and industry**. Test generation tools are software tools designed to automate the creation of test cases, typically based on source code, models, or specifications, with the goal of improving the efficiency and coverage of the testing process [Liu et al., 2024]. We conducted a multivocal literature review (MLR) and a survey to reach this goal. The MLR identified test generation tools reported in academic and industry sources, while the survey assessed their actual adoption by practitioners. Furthermore, during the survey, we also collected the advantages and disadvantages of each tool. The results of the MLR and the survey were used to propose a practical reference guide to support testing professionals in selecting the test generation tools to use.

Our findings reveal that the most frequently mentioned test generation tools in the literature are Monkey and Dynodroid. However, these tools are not actually used by the practitioners who participated in our survey, although many of them are aware of their existence. This indicates a gap between research and practice. In contrast, tools such as Postman, Selenium, and Cypress were identified as the most commonly used in the software industry. Participants highlighted several advantages of using test generation tools, including visibility of test execution results, availability of community support and documentation, traceability throughout the testing process, and integration with other development tools. At the same time, they pointed out challenges such as the inconsistency of automated tests, the need for regular maintenance, dependency on third-party reporting tools, and performance limitations. These findings underscore the need for stronger alignment between academic research and industrial needs, encouraging practical guidance for tool selection and greater focus on usability, interoperability, and sustainability in tool development.

Participants also emphasized challenges associated with test generation tools, including: (a) inconsistency in reliably capturing user actions or system responses—leading to false positives/negatives and reduced confidence in results; (b) the need for regular

maintenance to keep suites stable, especially when external integrations change; (c) dependence on third-party components or plugins for reporting and analysis, which complicates setup and governance; and (d) performance limitations in larger suites or end-to-end scenarios, which can slow feedback compared to unit tests or lightweight frameworks.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides background information and discusses related work on test generation tools, including existing classifications and prior comparative studies. Section 3 presents the research method employed to conduct this study, followed by the results obtained (Section 4). Then, Section 5 outlines the threats to the validity of our findings. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and discusses future work.

2 Background and Related Work

Software testing tools can be classified according to various dimensions, such as licensing model (open-source, commercial, or commercial trial), supported platforms (Web, Desktop, Mobile), and testing functionality (e.g., unit, regression, UI, load, API testing). Understanding these characteristics is necessary for selecting the appropriate tool for a specific project context [Okezie et al., 2019, Gamido & Gamido, 2019].

Following the classification proposed by Shaukat et al. [Shaukat et al., 2015], testing tools are grouped into the following categories: 1. **Open Source Tools:** Freely available tools that can be easily installed and used (e.g., Selenium). 2. **Commercial Tools:** Proprietary tools that require paid licenses (e.g., Quick Test Professional). 3. **Commercial Trial Tools:** Tools available under evaluation licenses, with limited-time access before requiring purchase.

Moreover, based on the SWEBOK guide [Bourque & Fairley, 2014], testing tools can be functionally categorized as follows: 1. **Test Harnesses:** Provide a controlled environment to initiate and monitor test execution. 2. **Test Generators:** Automatically generate test cases using random, model-based, or path-based approaches. 3. **Capture/Replay Tools:** Record and re-execute user interactions to automate tests. 4. **Assertion Tools (Oracles):** Verify whether the observed output matches the expected outcome. 5. **Coverage Analyzers:** Assess test completeness by measuring control flow or code element coverage. 6. **Trace Tools:** Record the history of execution paths. 7. **Regression Testing Tools:** Re-execute existing test cases after code changes. 8. **Reliability Assessment Tools:** Support the analysis of test results for reliability modeling. Several studies have investigated test generation tools through empirical analysis, experiments, or systematic reviews. Wang et al. [Wang et al., 2018] compared multiple Android UI test generation tools by measuring code coverage and bug detection in real-world apps. They observed that the Google Monkey tool achieved the highest method coverage in 22 out of 41 apps evaluated.

Shafique et al. [Shafique & Labiche, 2015] conducted a systematic review to identify the state of the art in Model-Based Testing (MBT) tools, particularly those relying on state-based models. Their goal was to help organizations evaluate and adopt suitable MBT tools.

Corradini et al. [Corradini et al., 2021] compared four REST API testing tools: RestTestGen, RESTler, bBOXRT, and RESTest, based on their robustness and test coverage. The study found that RESTler was the most effective, being the only tool to successfully test all 14 evaluated services. Earlier, Wang et al. [Wang & Offutt, 2009] compared three automated unit test generation tools JCrasher, TestGen4j, and JUB

using mutation score analysis. Their results indicated that automated tools performed comparably to manually created random tests.

Existing works have applied different evaluation approaches, ranging from controlled experiments [Wang & Offutt, 2009] to systematic literature reviews [Shafique & Labiche, 2015] and empirical benchmarking [Wang et al., 2018]. Most of these studies focus on a narrow set of tools or a specific testing domain (e.g., mobile, REST APIs), limiting their generalizability to broader software testing contexts. This study differs by combining a Multivocal Literature Review (MLR) with an industry-focused survey, encompassing both white and grey literature. This dual approach provides a broader perspective on tool usage and practitioner preferences across different application domains (API, Web, Mobile, Desktop).

This work contributes to the literature in three key ways: 1. **Tool Mapping:** It maps over 60 test generation tools identified through MLR, including classification by application type, testing type, and licensing model. 2. **Industry Feedback:** It analyzes practitioner perceptions through a survey involving software developers and testers from diverse backgrounds. 3. **Practical Guide:** It delivers a practical reference guide to support tool selection based on scenario-specific needs, bridging the gap between academic knowledge and industrial practice.

To our knowledge, this is the first study to offer such a comprehensive and structured overview of test generation tools, including both technical features and real-world adoption insights.

3 Study Settings

The main goal of this study is to identify and synthesize information regarding existing test generation tools. The results aim to support the development of a practical guide for software testing professionals. To achieve this objective, we formulated the following research questions (RQs):

RQ.1: What test generation tools are reported in the literature?

RQ.2: Are the test generation tools identified in the literature also employed in industry?

RQ.3: What are the advantages and challenges of using test generation tools?

To address **RQ1**, we conducted a Multivocal Literature Review (MLR) to identify test generation tools referenced in both academic and grey literature. To answer **RQ2** and **RQ3**, we designed and administered a survey targeting software practitioners. The aim of the survey was to understand their familiarity with the tools and to gather their perceptions regarding their advantages and challenges in practical settings.

3.1 Multivocal Literature Review

This study conducts a Multivocal Literature Review (MLR) to identify test generation tools. A MLR is a type of systematic review (i.e., a study that analyzes and synthesizes information from existing studies to generate new insights and conclusions) that combines both qualitative and quantitative data. It provides a broader perspective on the current state of the topic by including grey literature sources [Calderón et al., 2018]. Similar to traditional systematic literature reviews, MLRs are employed to address researcher bias

by striving to identify as many relevant studies as possible, using explicit methods to search, assess, and synthesize prior academic and non-academic work [Calderón et al., 2018, Pati & Lorusso, 2018]. To be effective, a literature review must ensure that the research domain is thoroughly understood, thereby providing a strong foundation for future investigations [Calderón et al., 2018].

With over 300 automated testing tools available on the market, it is important for professionals to continually expand their expertise as these tools evolve and mature. Practitioners must be able to identify the most suitable tool for each testing context, install it properly, and ensure it operates as expected [Gilchrist, 2009].

When conducting a literature review, the first step is to identify the need for such a review [Snyder, 2019]. In the context of this study, the need arises from the objective of developing a reference guide focused on test generation tools.

MLR considers peer-reviewed scientific articles published since 2015, along with relevant sources from the grey literature that discuss test generation tools. The search for studies was conducted through the following digital libraries: ACM Digital Library, Science Direct, Springer Link, IEEE Xplore Digital Library, and Google Scholar. The goal was to identify the advantages and challenges associated with using test generation tools. Based on the findings, we developed a practical reference guide to assist software professionals in overcoming the common obstacles of applying such tools in their projects.

3.1.1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

To be included in this study, a publication must be written in either English or Portuguese and must explicitly address the topic of test generation tools. The inclusion process was conducted in three stages, with an article advancing to the next stage only if it met the inclusion criteria of the current one. The stages are:

1. **Identification of studies through Snowballing and Backward Snowballing:** The study must have been published from the year 2015 onwards;
2. **Screening of titles, abstracts, and keywords:** These elements were reviewed to quickly determine the topic and scope of each study, enabling efficient filtering based on relevance to the research topic;
3. **Full-text reading:** The study must contribute novel insights or relevant data that answer at least one of the research questions. Thus, to be included, a study must address at least one of the following topics: Available test generation tools; Advantages and challenges of using test generation tools; and The relationship between developers and test generation tools.

In addition to studies that did not meet the inclusion criteria such as those published prior to 2015 we excluded inaccessible literature (i.e., not publicly available), search engine results flagged as duplicates or overly similar, and promotional content or vendor advertisements.

3.1.2 Quality Assessment

According to Garousi et al. [Garousi et al., 2019], the goal of quality assessment is to determine the reliability and bias level of a study. While formal literature typically goes

through a rigorous peer-review and publication process, grey literature is more diverse and less regulated, making its quality more challenging to assess. To evaluate the quality of grey literature sources, this study followed adapted guidelines proposed by Garousi et al. [Garousi et al., 2019], using the following assessment criteria:

1. **Authority of the Producer:** Is the organization or author reputable and experienced in the subject area (e.g., Software Engineering Institute - SEI)?
2. **Methodology:** Does the study have a clearly stated objective? Is it supported by reliable references? Does it address any of the predefined research questions?
3. **Objectivity:** Are the claims made in the study objective and evidence-based?
4. **Publication Date:** Is the publication date clearly stated?
5. **Originality:** Does the study add unique or new insights to the field? Does it confirm or refute existing literature?
6. **Source Type and Credibility:** Level 1 – High output control / High credibility: Books, journals, theses, government reports. Level 2 – Moderate output control / Moderate credibility: News articles, annual reports, presentations, Q&A websites, wiki articles, videos. Level 3 – Low output control / Low credibility: Blog posts, emails, tweets.

Each grey literature study was evaluated using the questions previously mentioned, receiving one point for each "yes" answer, for a maximum of 10 points based on the criteria of producer authority, methodology, objectivity, publication date, and originality. Additionally, a score of 0, 0.5, or 1 point was assigned according to the source's quality level (Level 3, 2, or 1, respectively).

To ensure a systematic quality assessment across all grey literature sources, we defined a quality threshold of 6 points. Any source scoring above this threshold was included in the study, while those scoring below were excluded.

Table 1 illustrates how the checklist is applied using three fictional examples of grey literature: GL1 (a blog post), GL2 (a magazine article), and GL3 (a YouTube video). Based on the checklist, GL1 was excluded due to a low score, while GL2 and GL3 met the quality threshold and were therefore included in the study.

3.1.3 Data Extraction

Following the definition of the review protocol, we initiated the execution of the multivocal literature review and the retrieval of relevant materials. The identification and selection of new studies were performed using forward and backward snowballing techniques, starting from a single seed paper: the work by Li and Yang [Li et al., 2017]. The snowballing procedures followed the guidelines proposed by Wohlin et al. [Wohlin, 2014].

Backward snowballing involves reviewing the reference list of the seed paper to identify new candidates for inclusion. Initially, all references that did not meet the inclusion criteria were discarded, along with those already examined in previous iterations. Each candidate study was fully explored before moving on to new documents, ensuring comprehensive extraction of information.

Forward snowballing, in turn, identifies new studies that cite the seed article. The selection and evaluation of these articles follow the same principles used in the backward

Criterion	Evaluation Questions	GL1	GL2	GL3
Producer Authority	Is the organization or individual reputable and experienced in the field?	0	1	0
	Has the organization or individual published other works in this domain?	1	1	1
Methodology	Is the study’s objective clearly stated?	0	1	1
	Is the study supported by credible references?	1	1	0
	Does the study address any of the research questions?	0	0	1
Objectivity	Are the claims objective or based on subjective opinions?	0	1	0
	Are the conclusions backed by data?	0	1	0
Publication Date	Is the publication date clearly indicated?	1	1	1
Originality	Does the study provide a unique contribution?	0	0	1
	Does it confirm or contradict findings from previous literature?	0	1	1
Quality Level		0	1	0.5
Total Score		3	9	6.5

Table 1: Quality assessment checklist for grey literature sources [Garousi et al., 2019]

process. For each study that met the inclusion criteria, we first reviewed the abstract and key sections of the paper to decide on its relevance. If selected, the full text was analyzed. Articles identified in each iteration were placed into a queue for the next round, ensuring traceability between documents and systematic exploration of the literature.

3.2 Survey Design

The survey aimed to collect insights from software professionals regarding the test generation tools they use, as well as the main advantages and challenges associated with their adoption. Software developers with diverse profiles—in terms of age and professional experience—were invited to participate. The only eligibility requirement was that the participant be a software developer or designer.

All authors of this paper were actively involved in designing and validating the survey instrument. The final version of the questionnaire comprised 10 items, all closed-ended, distributed across four thematic sections (Table 2). Each section was designed to address specific research questions and ensure the collection of structured, comparable data. The sections were organized as follows:

- **Part 1:** Collected demographic and professional profile information from participants, including age, education level, years of experience, development role, and programming languages used. This part corresponded to questions Q01 to Q06.
- **Part 2:** Focused on **RQ2**. Participants were presented with a list of 30 tools identified through the MLR and were asked to indicate their familiarity and usage level for each tool using a Likert scale [Bertram, 2007]: (a) I use often, (b) I use occasionally, (c) I know but don’t use, and (d) I don’t know. This part corresponded to question Q07 to Q08.

- **Part 3:** Addressed **RQ3** by asking participants to evaluate a list of potential advantages of using test generation tools. These advantages were identified from the literature [Risi, 2023d, Risi, 2023c, Risi, 2023b, Risi, 2023a, Risi, 2023e, Risi, 2023f]. Each item was rated as: (a) essential, (b) important, (c) useful, or (d) irrelevant. This section included questions Q09.
- **Part 4:** Also related to **RQ3**, this part focused on potential challenges and negative aspects of test generation tools. Participants rated each challenge as: (a) unacceptable, (b) challenging, (c) surmountable, or (d) irrelevant. This section comprised questions Q10.

Prior to full deployment, we conducted a pilot study to assess the clarity, structure, and comprehensibility of the survey. Five professionals in software development were invited to complete the survey and provide detailed feedback. Based on their suggestions, several improvements were made to the wording of the questions to ensure better understanding and eliminate ambiguity. The average completion time during the pilot was approximately 20 minutes. The pilot responses were not included in the final dataset.

The survey was implemented as an online questionnaire and administered in two rounds. The first round remained open for four weeks and collected 40 valid responses. To broaden the scope and enhance the diversity of participant profiles, a second round was conducted between August 15, 2025, and October 5, 2025, yielding 47 additional responses. Participation invitations in both rounds were distributed through the authors' personal and professional networks, as well as on social media platforms such as LinkedIn. The second round specifically targeted more experienced professionals in software development and testing, thereby increasing the representativeness of the sample.

All participants in the survey were professionals working in software development or testing. The list of test generation tools, as well as the set of advantages and challenges presented in the questionnaire, were derived entirely from the results of the Multivocal Literature Review (MLR). This ensured that the survey instrument was grounded in evidence from both academic and grey literature, and that the items evaluated by participants reflected tools and criteria already discussed in the broader testing community.

The full questionnaire and corresponding responses are available in the supplementary material at <https://zenodo.org/records/17329541>.

Part 1: Demographic Information	
Q01	What is your name?
Q02	What is your age group?
Q03	What is your highest level of education?
Q04	How many years have you been working with software development?
Q05	What is your role in the software development process?
Q06	Which programming languages do you work with?
Part 2: Tool Familiarity	
Q07	What is your familiarity with the following test generation tools from the academic literature?
Q08	What is your familiarity with the following test generation tools from the grey literature?
Part 3: Perceived Advantages	
Q09	How do you evaluate the following 19 advantages of test generation tools?
Part 4: Perceived Challenges	
Q10	How do you evaluate the following 13 challenges in using test generation tools?

Table 2: Survey Questions Grouped by Section

4 Multivocal Literature Review Results

4.1 Test generation tools (RQ.1)

Table 3 presents the set of test generation tools identified through the Multivocal Literature Review (MLR), along with their corresponding test type (e.g., black-box, grey-box, white-box) and the studies in which they were referenced. Among the 40+ tools listed, some appear significantly more frequently across the literature, indicating their widespread use or attention in the research community.

Monkey and Dynodroid are the most frequently cited tools, appearing in over 70 and 50 publications respectively. These tools are widely used for Android application testing and have been central to numerous comparative and empirical studies. Other highly referenced tools include Sapienz, Stoa, SwiftHand, Evodroid, and Humanoid, each cited in more than 20 studies. These tools primarily support black-box or grey-box testing and are commonly used in research on mobile app testing automation. Given the extensive number of tools reviewed, only the most cited and representative tools are discussed in detail in the subsequent subsections. This allows for a focused analysis while still acknowledging the diversity of available solutions.

Tool Name	Test Type	List of Studies
Monkey	Black box	[Choudhary et al., 2015], [Amalfitano et al., 2012], [Machiry et al., 2013], [Choi et al., 2013] [Hao et al., 2014], [Azim & Neamtiu, 2013], [Bhoraskar et al., 2014], [Bierma et al., 2014], [Amalfitano et al., 2014], [Anand et al., 2012], [Mahmood et al., 2014], [Yang et al., 2013b], [Clapp et al., 2016], [Gomez et al., 2013], [Jensen et al., 2013], [Kochhar et al., 2015], [Mao et al., 2016], [Mirzaei et al., 2015], [Qin et al., 2016], [Ravindranath et al., 2014], [Yang et al., 2013a], [Jeon & Foster, 2012] [Banerjee et al., 2014], [Yan, 2014], [Su et al., 2021a], [Dong et al., 2020a], [Li et al., 2019], [Wang et al., 2018], [Wang et al., 2021a], [Daragh & Malek, 2021], [Almeida et al., 2019], [Yasin et al., 2021], [Pilgun et al., 2020], [Cai et al., 2020], [Köroglu & Sen, 2019], [Peng et al., 2021], [Wanwarang et al., 2020], [Yasin et al., 2020], [Ma et al., 2023], [Ibrahim et al., 2021], [Sun, 2021], [Osorio Riaño et al., 2020], [Forte, 2017], [Liu et al., 2023a], [Feng et al., 2023], [Lv et al., 2022], [Ran et al., 2023], [Sun et al., 2023], [Zhao et al., 2022a], [Hu et al., 2023], [Liu et al., 2023b], [Su et al., 2021b], [Ghorbani et al., 2023], [Peng et al., 2022], [Ran et al., 2022], [Zhong et al., 2023], [Ngo et al., 2022], [Ngo et al., 2023], [Dong et al., 2020b], [Guo et al., 2020], [da Costa et al., 2022], [Peng et al., 2023], [Zhao et al., 2021], [Zhao, 2020], [Sun et al., 2021], [Wang et al., 2020], [Lai & Rubin, 2019], [He et al., 2020], [Wang et al., 2021b], [Yan et al., 2021], [Doyle et al., 2021], [Zhao et al., 2022b], [Pilgun, 2020b], [Hatas et al., 2019], [Behrang & Orso, 2020], [Yang et al., 2019], [Gebrekstos, 2022], [SPEK, 2021], [Huang, 2008], [Yu et al., 2023], [Escobar Velásquez, 2023], [Pantoja Gómez, 2022], [Valbuena Bautista, 2023], [Moreno et al., 2023], [Pilgun, 2020a].
Dynodroid	Black box	[Choudhary et al., 2015], [Machiry et al., 2013], [Choi et al., 2013], [Choudhary et al., 2015], [Amalfitano et al., 2014], [Mahmood et al., 2014], [Clapp et al., 2016], [Jensen et al., 2013], [Kochhar et al., 2015], [Mao et al., 2016], [Mirzaei et al., 2015], [Ravindranath et al., 2014], [Banerjee et al., 2014], [Dong et al., 2020a], [Li et al., 2019], [Wang et al., 2018], [Daragh & Malek, 2021], [Yasin et al., 2021], [Pilgun et al., 2020], [Cai et al., 2020], [Peng et al., 2021], [Wanwarang et al., 2020], [Yasin et al., 2020], [Arnatovich & Wang, 2018], [Forte, 2017], [Liu et al., 2023a], [Zhao et al., 2022a], [Ghorbani et al., 2023], [Guo et al., 2020], [Peng et al., 2023], [Zhao et al., 2021], [Zhao, 2020], [Wang et al., 2020], [Lai & Rubin, 2019], [He et al., 2020], [Doyle et al., 2021], [Pilgun, 2020b], [Hatas et al., 2019], [Behrang & Orso, 2020], [Yang et al., 2019], [Gebrekstos, 2022], [SPEK, 2021], [Huang, 2008], [Escobar Velásquez, 2023], [Pantoja Gómez, 2022], [Valbuena Bautista, 2023], [Moreno et al., 2023].
SwiftHand	Black box	[Choudhary et al., 2015], [Choi et al., 2013], [Clapp et al., 2016], [Mao et al., 2016], [Mirzaei et al., 2015], [Dong et al., 2020a], [Wang et al., 2018], [Pilgun et al., 2020], [Wanwarang et al., 2020], [Arnatovich & Wang, 2018], [Sun, 2021], [Forte, 2017], [Wang et al., 2020], [Wang et al., 2022], [Pilgun, 2020b], [Behrang & Orso, 2020], [Gebrekstos, 2022], [Huang, 2008], [Escobar Velásquez, 2023], [Pantoja Gómez, 2022], [Moreno et al., 2023].
Puma	Black box	[Choudhary et al., 2015], [Hao et al., 2014], [Clapp et al., 2016], [Mao et al., 2016], [Dong et al., 2020a], [Li et al., 2019], [Yasin et al., 2021], [Cai et al., 2020], [Wanwarang et al., 2020], [Yasin et al., 2020], [Sun, 2021], [Forte, 2017], [Guo et al., 2020], [da Costa et al., 2022], [Zhao et al., 2021], [Behrang & Orso, 2020], [Escobar Velásquez, 2023], [Pantoja Gómez, 2022], [Valbuena Bautista, 2023], [Moreno et al., 2023].

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Tool Name	Test Type	List of Studies
Evodroid	Grey box	[Choudhary et al., 2015], [Choi et al., 2013], [Mahmood et al., 2014], [Clapp et al., 2016], [Mao et al., 2016], [Mirzaei et al., 2015], [Dong et al., 2020a], [Daragh & Malek, 2021], [Wanwarang et al., 2020], [Arnatovich & Wang, 2018], [Sun, 2021], [Forte, 2017], [Su et al., 2021b], [Ghorbani et al., 2023], [Zhong et al., 2023], [Zhao et al., 2021], [Wang et al., 2020], [Pilgun, 2020b], [Hatas et al., 2019], [Behrang & Orso, 2020], [Yang et al., 2019], [Gebrekstos, 2022], [Huang, 2008], [Moreno et al., 2023].
AndroidRipper	Black box	[Amalfitano et al., 2012], [Bhoraskar et al., 2014], [Amalfitano et al., 2014], [Yang et al., 2013b], [Jensen et al., 2013], [Mao et al., 2016], [Yang et al., 2013a], [Yan, 2014], [Dong et al., 2020a], [Almeida et al., 2019], [Wanwarang et al., 2020], [Yasin et al., 2020], [Forte, 2017], [Zhao et al., 2021], [Pan et al., 2023], [Doyle et al., 2021].
MobiGUITAR	Black box	[Choudhary et al., 2015], [Amalfitano et al., 2014], [Clapp et al., 2016], [Kochhar et al., 2015], [Qin et al., 2016], [Wanwarang et al., 2020], [Arnatovich & Wang, 2018], [Sun, 2021], [Forte, 2017], [Guo et al., 2020], [Doyle et al., 2021], [Gebrekstos, 2022].
Randooop	Grey box	[Gross et al., 2012b], [Gross et al., 2012a], [Fraser & Arcuri, 2012], [Brunetto et al., 2021], [Potuzak & Lipka, 2023], [Galler & Aichernig, 2014], [Devroey et al., 2020].
EvoSuitee	Black box	[Gross et al., 2012b], [Gross et al., 2012a], [Fraser & Arcuri, 2012], [Just et al., 2014], [Ngo et al., 2022], [Brunetto et al., 2021], [Gebrekstos, 2022], [Potuzak & Lipka, 2023], [Moreno et al., 2023], [Devroey et al., 2020].
A3E	Grey box	[Mao et al., 2016], [Mirzaei et al., 2015], [Ravindranath et al., 2014], [Yan, 2014], [Dong et al., 2020a], [Wang et al., 2018], [Yasin et al., 2021], [Yasin et al., 2020], [Arnatovich & Wang, 2018], [Sun, 2021], [Forte, 2017], [Liu et al., 2023a], [Zhao et al., 2022a], [Guo et al., 2020], [Zhao, 2020], [Lai & Rubin, 2019], [Pan et al., 2023], [Doyle et al., 2021], [Behrang & Orso, 2020], [Yang et al., 2019], [Huang, 2008], [Escobar Velásquez, 2023], [Pantoja Gómez, 2022], [Moreno et al., 2023].
Orbit	Grey box	[Mao et al., 2016], [Ravindranath et al., 2014], [Dong et al., 2020a], [Yasin et al., 2021], [Wanwarang et al., 2020], [Forte, 2017], [Guo et al., 2020], [Behrang & Orso, 2020], [Yang et al., 2019], [Huang, 2008].
JMeter	–	[Nistor et al., 2013], [Arnatovich & Wang, 2018], [Yoo & Harman, 2012].
Robotium	Black box	[Kochhar et al., 2015], [Zadgaonkar, 2013], [Adamsen et al., 2015], [Yan, 2014], [Almeida et al., 2019], [Forte, 2017], [Lai & Rubin, 2019], [Pan et al., 2023], [SPEK, 2021], [Escobar Velásquez, 2023], [Pantoja Gómez, 2022].
PEX	Grey box	[Mirshokraie et al., 2013], [Fraser & Arcuri, 2012], [Anand, 2012], [Park et al., 2012], [Brunetto et al., 2021], [Galler & Aichernig, 2014].
Humanoid	Black box	[Su et al., 2021a], [Li et al., 2019], [Daragh & Malek, 2021], [Yasin et al., 2021], [Cai et al., 2020], [Yasin et al., 2020], [Ma et al., 2023], [Liu et al., 2023b], [Peng et al., 2022], [Ngo et al., 2023], [da Costa et al., 2022], [Peng et al., 2023], [Zhao et al., 2021], [Zhao, 2020], [Zhao et al., 2022b], [Yang et al., 2019], [Escobar Velásquez, 2023], [Pantoja Gómez, 2022], [Cheng, 2022].
Ape	Black box	[Su et al., 2021a], [Dong et al., 2020a], [Ma et al., 2023], [Liu et al., 2023a], [Feng et al., 2023], [Lv et al., 2022], [Ran et al., 2023], [Zhao et al., 2022a], [Hu et al., 2023], [Liu et al., 2023b], [Su et al., 2021b], [Ghorbani et al., 2023], [Peng et al., 2022], [Ngo et al., 2022], [Ngo et al., 2023], [Guo et al., 2020], [Peng et al., 2023], [Wang et al., 2020], [Wang et al., 2022], [Lai & Rubin, 2019], [Wang et al., 2021b], [Cheng, 2022].

...continued

Tool Name	Test Type	List of Studies
TimeMachine	Black box	[Su et al., 2021a], [Dong et al., 2020a], [Liu et al., 2023a], [Liu et al., 2023b], [Ghorbani et al., 2023], [Peng et al., 2022], [Ngo et al., 2023], [Dong et al., 2020b], [Escobar Velásquez, 2023], [Pantoja Gómez, 2022], [Cheng, 2022].
Sapienz	Grey box	[Li et al., 2019], [Wang et al., 2018], [Daragh & Malek, 2021], [Yasin et al., 2021], [Pilgun et al., 2020], [Cai et al., 2020], [Yasin et al., 2020], [Arnatovich & Wang, 2018], [Ma et al., 2023], [Ibrahim et al., 2021], [Sun, 2021], [Forte, 2017], [Liu et al., 2023a], [Zhao et al., 2022a], [Hu et al., 2023], [Liu et al., 2023b], [Su et al., 2021b], [Ghorbani et al., 2023], [Peng et al., 2022], [Zhong et al., 2023], [Dong et al., 2020b], [Guo et al., 2020], [Zhao et al., 2021], [Zhao, 2020], [Wang et al., 2020], [Lai & Rubin, 2019], [He et al., 2020], [Zhao et al., 2022b], [Pilgun, 2020b], [Hatas et al., 2019], [Behrang & Orso, 2020], [Yang et al., 2019], [Gebrekrestos, 2022], [SPEK, 2021], [Huang, 2008], [Escobar Velásquez, 2023], [Pantoja Gómez, 2022], [Valbuena Bautista, 2023], [Moreno et al., 2023].
Stoat	Black box	[Li et al., 2019], [Wang et al., 2018], [Machiry et al., 2013], [Yasin et al., 2021], [Pilgun et al., 2020], [Wanwarang et al., 2020], [Yasin et al., 2020], [Arnatovich & Wang, 2018], [Ma et al., 2023], [Sun, 2021], [Liu et al., 2023a], [Feng et al., 2023], [Lv et al., 2022], [Ran et al., 2023], [Zhao et al., 2022a], [Liu et al., 2023b], [Su et al., 2021b], [Ghorbani et al., 2023], [Peng et al., 2022], [Zhong et al., 2023], [Dong et al., 2020b], [Guo et al., 2020], [Zhao, 2020], [Lai & Rubin, 2019], [He et al., 2020], [Pan et al., 2023], [Doyle et al., 2021], [Zhao et al., 2022b], [Pilgun, 2020b], [Behrang & Orso, 2020], [Yang et al., 2019], [Gebrekrestos, 2022], [SPEK, 2021], [Huang, 2008], [Escobar Velásquez, 2023], [Pantoja Gómez, 2022], [Valbuena Bautista, 2023], [Moreno et al., 2023].
C++Test	White box	[Brunetto et al., 2021], [Hatas et al., 2019], [Galler & Aichernig, 2014].
JTest	Grey box	[Potuzak & Lipka, 2023], [Galler & Aichernig, 2014].
MuJava	White box	[Hao et al., 2012], [Xu et al., 2015], [Zhang et al., 2016].
SoapUI	Black box	[Bures, 2014]
Korat	Grey box	[Galler & Aichernig, 2014], [Xu et al., 2015].

Table 3: Tools identified in the literature

Monkey: This tool is part of the Android developer toolkit and therefore requires no additional installation effort. It implements the most basic random strategy, as it considers the application under test to be a black box and can only generate user interface (UI) events [Choudhary et al., 2015]. It sends random types of input events to random locations on the screen without considering its Graphical User Interface (GUI) structure [Li et al., 2019]. Monkey is widely used in the industry for stress testing because it is easy to use and compatible with any version of Android, making it a popular basis for evaluating new testing techniques [Su et al., 2021a].

Dynodroid: It can generate UI and system inputs and allows you to combine human and machine inputs [Machiry et al., 2013]. It can generate system events and check which ones are relevant to the application. It can select events that have been selected less frequently (frequency strategy) and take context into account (BiasedRandom strategy), i.e. events that are relevant in more contexts will be selected more frequently [Li et al., 2019].

SoapUI: Free, open source, cross-platform API testing tool that lets you create and run automated functional, regression, compliance, and load tests quickly and easily [Kumar et al., 2015]. SoapUI also allows you to carry out non-functional tests, such as performance and security tests [Kumar et al., 2015].

Stoat: It combines static and dynamic analysis to build a model of the application and then uses the generated model to guide the exploration of the application during testing. Stoat injects, in addition to UI events, system events to improve the effectiveness of test input generation [Behrang & Orso, 2020].

Sapienz: It uses a multi-objective search-based approach to automatically explore and optimize test sequences, minimizing duration while maximizing coverage and fault detection [Behrang & Orso, 2020]. Sapienz explores application components using specific GUIs and complex sequences of input events with a predefined pattern [Yasin et al., 2021]. This predefined pattern is called a motif gene that captures the testers' experience. It thus produces greater code coverage by concatenating the atomic events [Yasin et al., 2021].

The following tools were identified in the grey literature:

Selenium: Framework with many tools and plug-ins for testing web applications [Umar & Zhanfang, 2019]. It is popular in the area of open-source test automation, partly due to its large and active development and user community [Umar & Zhanfang, 2019]. It provides support for various operating systems and different programming languages [Ateşoğulları & Mishra, 2020]. It can be integrated with various frameworks to provide a hybrid framework, which makes testing simpler [Islam, 2016]. Some advantages of Selenium include its ease of use and flexibility allowing users to debug and set breakpoints in test cases [Okezie et al., 2019]. Some challenges include the lack of support for conditional and iteration statements, database testing and no error handling capabilities [Okezie et al., 2019].

Appium: Open source cross-platform mobile testing tool that allows developers to write tests on various platforms, such as iOS and Android [Okezie et al., 2019]. Provides REST API testing [Ateşoğulları & Mishra, 2020]. Appium focuses on testing user interaction with the content of web applications for mobile devices. The test results are used to evaluate the accuracy and user engagement with the mobile application, as well as the ease of use or availability of features [Okezie et al., 2019]. There are client libraries in Java, Ruby, Python, PHP, JavaScript, and C#, which support Appium extensions to the WebDriver protocol [Ateşoğulları & Mishra, 2020].

Test Complete: Integrated commercial platform for testing desktop, mobile, and web applications [Umar & Zhanfang, 2019]. It offers some important test automation features, such as keyword and data-driven testing, cross-browser, API, and continuous integration (CI) integrations [Umar & Zhanfang, 2019]. It has features that ensure tests are repeated once after recording [Ateşoğulları & Mishra, 2020]. The creation of catchphrases used for testing is visual, simple, and requires no programming skills [Okezie et al., 2019]. The script requires an understanding of script instructions but allows for more dominant and adaptable tests [Okezie et al., 2019].

Cucumber: It supports different languages, such as Java.net and Ruby. Test scenarios can be entered in plain text in English. It therefore requires no code information and offers ease of use [Ateşoğulları & Mishra, 2020].

Ranorex Studio: Testing tool and framework [Gunasekaran & Bargavi, 2015]. It is one of the most popular commercial tools for building and running automated web and GUI tests [S, 2016]. It allows end-to-end testing on different devices such as desktop, web, and mobile [Ateşoğulları & Mishra, 2020]. Ranorex consists of but is not limited to, the following features: reusable test codes, integration with various tools, GUI recognition, recording and playback, bug detection, and so on [Okezie et al., 2019]. Ranorex is easy to use, inexpensive, and can be used by any testing team [Okezie et al., 2019].

Katalon: Automated testing framework that offers a comprehensive set of features to implement complete automated testing solutions [Umar & Zhanfang, 2019]. Built on

the Selenium and Appium open source frameworks [Umar & Zhanfang, 2019]. It does not support distributed testing, supporting only Web, Mobile, and API automation tests. provides exports to C#, Java, Ruby, Python, Groovy or Robot Framework [Ateşoğulları & Mishra, 2020].

Cypress: End-to-end testing tool for modern web test automation based on JavaScript. It operates directly in the browser using a DOM manipulation approach, interacting directly with the application being tested [Pragya Sen, 2023]. It has support for network traffic control which allows testing of extreme scenarios without involving the server [Advaith Aditya Chevuturu, 2022]. Supports only JavaScript test case scripts and does not provide support for multiple tabs [Pragya Sen, 2023].

Postman: Platform that supports all stages of an API's lifecycle: development, testing, publishing, and documentation [Dimoski et al., 2022]. It offers automated testing and integration in the CI/CD (continuous integration/continuous delivery) pipeline where users can create custom test suites in JavaScript, parameterize requests, run the tests and debug, as well as exploratory testing where users can use scripts to send asynchronous requests, chain requests to create test scenarios and document the findings [Dimoski et al., 2022].

Apache JMeter: Open source software that allows load testing, functional testing, and performance measurement [Dimoski et al., 2022]. For load testing, there is a CLI mode that allows you to load tests from any Java-compatible operating system, it also offers multi-threading support and CI support [Dimoski et al., 2022].

Robot Framework: Keyword-based test automation framework [Stresnjak & Hocenski, 2011]. Test cases are stored in HTML files and make use of keywords implemented in test libraries to drive the software under test, test suites are created from files and directory [Stresnjak & Hocenski, 2011].

RQ.1 Summary: The most cited test generation tools in the literature were Monkey and Dynodroid, followed by Sapienz and Stoa.

4.2 Test generation tools used in industry (RQ.2)

To answer RQ.2 and RQ.3, we conducted a survey. The first round of data collection was available online for four weeks, yielding 40 valid responses and an average completion time of approximately 10 minutes. To expand the scope and representativeness of the study, a second round of data collection was conducted between August 15, 2025, and October 5, 2025, resulting in 47 additional responses. The second round aimed to include more experienced professionals, particularly those working in software development and testing. Across both rounds, the average response time was approximately 15 minutes. All responses were consolidated into a single dataset and organized in a spreadsheet for subsequent analysis. Therefore, the combined dataset now comprises 87 responses.

Regarding the profile of the participants (Q01 to Q06), the survey gathered a diverse group of 87 software practitioners with varying backgrounds and levels of experience. Most respondents (57.5%) were aged between 30 and 50 years, while 28.7% were between 21 and 25 years old. This age distribution reflects a balanced composition between early-career and mid-career professionals. In terms of education, 60% of participants hold at least an undergraduate degree, and 40% have completed postgraduate studies (specialization, master's, or Ph.D.), indicating a well-qualified sample of professionals.

When considering professional experience, the majority of participants (64.4%) reported having more than four years of experience in software development, including 27.6% with 11–20 years of experience. These results highlight a mature professional profile, with participants who are actively engaged in the development and maintenance of software systems. Regarding their professional roles, 64.4% of respondents work primarily in software development and testing, distributed among full-stack developers (33.3%), general developers (31%), and testers (20.7%). A smaller portion of respondents occupy project management or coordination positions (9.2%), showing that the sample captures both technical and managerial perspectives. Table 4 summarizes the demographic and professional characteristics of the participants.

Age Group	#	%
<21 years old	4	4.6
21–25 years old	25	28.7
25–30 years old	8	9.2
30–40 years old	28	32.2
40–50 years old	22	25.3
>50 years old	0	0
Educational Level	#	%
Undergraduate student	22	25.3
Graduated	30	34.5
Postgraduate (Specialization)	18	20.7
Master	12	13.8
PhD	5	5.7
Experience	#	%
≥ 1 year	4	4.6
1–3 years	27	31.0
4–10 years	32	36.8
11–20 years	24	27.6
More than 20 years	0	0
Role	#	%
Front-end Developer	3	3.4
Back-end Developer	2	2.3
Full-stack Developer	29	33.3
Tester	18	20.7
Developer (General)	27	31.0
Project Manager	8	9.2

Table 4: Demographic Profile and Programming Languages of All Survey Respondents (n=87)

With respect to programming languages, the most frequently mentioned by the participants were JavaScript, Python, and Java, followed by TypeScript, C#, and C/C++. These languages represent the dominant technologies in contemporary software development and testing environments. Respondents aged between 30 and 50 years reported a greater presence of enterprise-oriented languages, such as Java and C#, while younger professionals demonstrated broader familiarity with web development technologies, particularly JavaScript and TypeScript. Less common languages such as Go, Kotlin, and Rust appeared only among the most experienced professionals, suggesting an exploratory adoption of modern and performance-oriented technologies. Table 5 presents the distribution of programming languages by age group.

Building upon this demographic overview, the following questions explores par-

ticipants' familiarity with software testing tools, focusing on the distinction between tools identified in the academic literature and those more widely adopted in professional practice.

To answer RQ.2, we asked the survey participants to indicate their familiarity with the testing tools (Q07) identified in the multivocal literature review. Figure 1 displays the tools most frequently referenced in the academic literature and their adoption among practitioners, distinguishing between tools that are used and those that are known but not used.

Programming Language	Age (years old)				
	≤ 21	21–25	25–30	30–40	40–50
JavaScript	3	19	6	10	7
Python	3	10	5	9	5
Java	1	8	3	13	10
TypeScript	0	8	3	5	3
C#	0	2	2	6	5
C/C++	1	2	1	4	3
PHP	0	3	1	3	2
Go	0	0	1	3	2
Kotlin	0	0	0	2	1
Rust	0	0	0	1	1
Ruby	0	1	0	1	0

Table 5: Programming Languages by Age Group of All Respondents (n=87)

Among the tools listed, JTest (30%) and C++Test (10%) stand out as the most widely used by professionals. Moderate levels of use were also reported for JMeter (14%), SoapUI (9%), and MuJava (5%). In contrast, tools such as Monkey, Dynodroid, AndroidRipper, SwiftHand, and PEX did not register any active usage among respondents, reinforcing their limited presence in industrial practice.

Recognition without usage remains considerably higher for several tools. C++Test (38%), JTest (30%), JMeter (30%), and SoapUI (28%) are relatively well known by practitioners, even if not widely adopted. Similarly, academic tools such as Randoop (20%) and EvoSuite (12%) show notable awareness despite low practical usage rates.

These results reinforce a persistent gap between academic visibility and industrial adoption. Many tools frequently cited in research such as Monkey, Dynodroid, and SwiftHand are unfamiliar to practitioners or lack evidence of active use. Possible explanations include limited documentation, poor usability, or lack of maintenance over time. Conversely, enterprise-supported tools like JTest and C++Test, which offer commercial support and integration with corporate ecosystems, show greater adoption in practice even with lower academic visibility.

Overall, these findings highlight the importance of bridging the gap between research-oriented tool development and industrial needs. Academic initiatives could benefit from closer collaboration with practitioners to improve usability, integration, and dissemination of testing tools in real-world software projects.

Figure 2 presents the test generation tools identified in the grey literature (Q08), highlighting both their usage and recognition among all 87 survey respondents. The results show that Postman remains the most widely used tool, adopted by 74% of participants, confirming its dominant position in API testing and automation workflows. Selenium (50%) and Cypress (46%) also demonstrate strong adoption, reaffirming their relevance

Figure 1: Tools used versus tools known by practitioners (n=87)

as essential tools for web testing and continuous integration environments. Other tools that exhibit moderate levels of use include Apache JMeter (26%), Cucumber (23%), and Playwright (15%), reflecting a growing interest in tools that support scriptless or code-driven test automation.

In terms of familiarity, even when not actively used, several tools show high recognition among practitioners. Cucumber stands out as the best-known tool overall, with 49% of respondents reporting awareness despite limited use. Appium (33%), Robot Framework (31%), Katalon (25%), and Puppeteer (30%) also present notable recognition levels, indicating that they are frequently considered in tool selection and evaluation processes, even if not part of the respondents' daily workflows.

Conversely, some tools continue to display low visibility or minimal adoption. Ranorex Studio, Lambda Test, Eggplant, and ACCELQ were each used or known by fewer than 15% of participants, suggesting restricted dissemination within professional contexts. These results align with the observation that commercial or proprietary solutions, especially those with steeper learning curves or licensing costs, tend to have lower penetration in practice.

Overall, the dataset reinforces a clear practitioner preference for open source, community-supported, and easily integrable tools. Solutions like Postman, Selenium, and Cypress exemplify this trend by offering accessible interfaces, frequent updates, and compatibility with modern CI/CD pipelines. The distinction between recognition and actual use also highlights a recurrent gap between awareness and adoption, emphasizing the importance of usability, documentation, and ecosystem integration in practitioners' tool selection decisions.

Figure 2: Tools identified in grey literature: usage versus awareness among practitioners (combined dataset, n=87)

RQ.2 Summary: The combined results from both survey rounds (n=87) indicate that many tools frequently mentioned in the academic literature are not widely adopted or recognized in industrial practice. Practitioners tend to favor open-source and community-supported solutions that integrate well with modern development pipelines, such as Postman, Selenium, and Cypress. In contrast, several academic tools, including Monkey and Dynodroid, remain largely unused outside research contexts. These findings reinforce the gap between research visibility and real-world applicability of testing tools.

4.3 Advantages and challenges (RQ.3)

Parts 3 and 4 of the survey were designed to answer RQ.3. Specifically, Questions Q09 and Q10 explored practitioners' perceptions of the benefits and difficulties associated with test generation tools. Participants were asked to evaluate a list of general-purpose features that are commonly found in such tools. These features were not tied to any specific tool, allowing participants to express their views based on overall experience rather than tool-specific knowledge.

For advantages (Q09), participants rated 19 features according to their relevance when selecting a test generation tool: essential, important, useful, or irrelevant. The results, presented in Figure 3, reveal that professionals tend to prioritize aspects that directly improve visibility, integration, and efficiency within testing workflows. The most valued advantages were visual logs (56%), which facilitate monitoring and debugging during test execution; traceability (42%), which ensures full tracking of test results and

their relationship to system requirements; and integration libraries (38%), which enable interoperability between testing tools and other components of the development pipeline. These elements were rated as essential or important by the majority of respondents, reflecting a strong preference for tools that streamline collaboration and continuous testing.

Features such as support for multiple platforms (50%), automation of commands (46%), and an active community (44%) were also considered important, indicating that practitioners value flexibility and long-term sustainability when adopting testing tools. On the other hand, aspects like already-known structure and recording and playback capabilities were viewed as less critical, suggesting that experienced professionals tend to rely more on customization and scripting than on pre-defined templates or record-based mechanisms.

It is also noteworthy that the open-source characteristic was consistently associated with transparency, adaptability, and collective improvement rather than cost-related factors. This reinforces a cultural preference among practitioners for tools that promote knowledge sharing, extensibility, and active community involvement within the software testing ecosystem.

Figure 3: Perceived advantages in using test generation tools

For challenges (Q10), participants evaluated 13 commonly reported issues associated with the adoption and maintenance of test generation tools, using the same four-point scale: unacceptable, challenging, surmountable, or irrelevant. Figure 4 illustrates the distribution of responses across these categories. The most critical concern identified was the inconsistency of tests (68%), particularly in tools that fail to reliably capture

user actions or system responses during execution. Such inconsistencies can lead to incomplete or unreliable test results, reducing confidence in automation outcomes.

Maintenance effort and dependency on external or third-party components were also regarded as significant challenges, reflecting practitioners' concern about the sustainability and operational overhead of test automation. Other recurrent issues include limited support, low performance in large-scale testing, and vendor or version lock-in, which can restrict flexibility in adapting tools to evolving project needs.

In contrast, aspects such as the cost of tools and delays in the release of new features were considered less critical by most respondents, suggesting that professionals tend to prioritize reliability, maintainability, and integration stability over licensing or update frequency. Overall, these findings indicate that experienced practitioners place greater emphasis on the long-term robustness and adaptability of test generation tools rather than on short-term usability or cost factors.

Figure 4: Perceived challenges in using test generation tools

RQ.3 Summary: Practitioners emphasized that the most valued advantages in test generation tools are the presence of visual logs that facilitate monitoring and debugging, the availability of integration libraries that enhance interoperability with other systems, and the assurance of traceability throughout the testing process. These characteristics contribute to improved visibility, efficiency, and collaboration in testing workflows. Conversely, the main challenges identified include inconsistent test execution, high maintenance effort, and dependency on third-party components for reporting or analysis. Overall, the findings highlight that professionals value reliability, integration capability, and transparency over cost or ease of use when adopting test generation tools.

4.4 Practical Reference Guide

The proposed reference guide aims to help test practitioners select a test generation tool suitable for the context of each project. The guide is organized by testing domain (API, Mobile, Desktop, and Web), allowing professionals to identify and compare tools according to test type (Functional, Regression, UI, Load) and licensing model (Open Source or Commercial). This structure enables practitioners to quickly locate tools that match specific technical requirements and project constraints. Each section presents comparative information on ease of learning, community support, record–playback capabilities, scripting languages, reporting features, and supported interfaces, thereby assisting practitioners in making informed and context-aware decisions, as shown in Figure 5.

Beyond serving as a catalog of options, the guide is intended to function as a practical decision-support instrument that reflects the realities of contemporary software engineering. Its design encourages the integration of testing tools within continuous integration and continuous delivery (CI/CD) pipelines, promoting automation, traceability, and feedback throughout the development lifecycle. By aligning the selection of test generation tools with DevOps principles and collaborative workflows, the guide contributes to more efficient, scalable, and quality-driven testing practices in industry settings.

Figure 6 presents the proposed guide in the context of API testing. Table 6 presents a comparative overview of recommended tools for API testing based on the findings from the multivocal literature review and practitioner survey. The tools are grouped into two blocks, each marked with a grey row for visual clarity. The first block includes SoapUI, Katalon, and Postman, which are commonly used for functional and integration API testing. The second block includes JMeter, TestComplete, and LoadRunner, which are more frequently employed for performance and load testing scenarios. Each tool is compared across six dimensions: ease of learning, community support, record-playback capabilities, supported scripting languages, report generation features, and supported API request types. This structured comparison aims to help practitioners identify the most suitable tool for their specific project needs, taking into account both functional and non-functional testing requirements.

Figure 5: Mobile Testing Guide

Tool	Characteristics					
	Ease of Learning	Community Support	Record-Playback	Scripting Language	Report Generation	API Request Support
SoapUI	Basic features are easy to use; more complex scenarios require a deeper understanding of the tool	Active community with many forums and resources for support and guidance	Not supported	Groovy and JavaScript	Built-in feature that generates reports after test execution, including test counts, pass/fail status, and graphs	SOAP/WSDL, REST, GraphQL, JMS
Katalon	Requires entry-level knowledge of Java/-Groovy for debugging	Limited support	Web Recorder Utility captures user actions and converts them into backend-executable code	Groovy	Presents analytics in built-in reports that can be exported to PDF, HTML, Excel, or CSV formats	REST: Swagger, OpenAPI 3.0 & WADL, SOAP (1.1 & 1.2), GraphQL, Authentication: Basic, Bearer, OAuth 1.0, OAuth 2.0, NTLM

Tool	Characteristics					
	Ease of Learning	Community Support	Record-Playback	Scripting Language	Report Generation	API Request Support
Postman	Easy for developers and testers to understand and use	Large and active community of users and developers	Not supported	JavaScript	API documentation includes full details such as authentication methods, parameters, request/response bodies, headers, and examples	HTTP, REST, SOAP, GraphQL, WebSockets. Authentication: OAuth 1.2/2.0, AWS Signature, Hawk
JMeter	GUI is user-friendly; however, advanced features may have a steep learning curve	Strong community with many plugins to extend functionality	Supports record and playback; scenarios can be edited using JavaScript. Blazemeter plugin enhances editing of recorded scripts	Groovy, Beanshell, JavaScript, Java	Includes listeners and reporting tools to analyze results and performance issues	HTTP, HTTPS, FTP, JDBC, SOAP, REST, WebSocket
TestComplete	Relatively steep learning curve	Active and helpful user community	Allows HTTP requests to be recorded and played back	JavaScript	Provides visual logs and screenshots, plus detailed reports for test analysis	REST
LoadRunner	Steep learning curve	Strong community and professional support	Supported. Captures application operations based on communication protocols	C	Graphical representation of results via LoadRunner Analysis	HTTP, HTTPS

Table 6: Recommended tools for API testing

Figure 6: API Testing Guide

5 Threats to Validity

To ensure a rigorous interpretation of the study results, we considered four types of validity threats, as defined by Wohlin et al. [Wohlin et al., 2012]: conclusion, internal, construct, and external validity. Below, we discuss how each of these threats may impact our study and the mitigation strategies adopted.

Conclusion Validity: A potential limitation is that not all relevant test generation tools were identified for inclusion in the practical reference guide. To mitigate this, we conducted a multivocal literature review using multiple digital libraries and incorporated both white and grey literature sources. This approach increased the comprehensiveness and diversity of the tools collected.

Internal Validity: As the survey was distributed asynchronously and completed without supervision, there is a risk that some participants responded without full attention or care. To reduce this threat, we included a disclaimer at the beginning of the questionnaire emphasizing the voluntary and anonymous nature of participation and encouraging thoughtful responses.

Construct Validity: The predominance of mobile-oriented tools in the literature may have influenced the composition of the tool set identified. To address this, we deliberately complemented our analysis with grey literature sources that focus on API, desktop, and web testing, allowing us to diversify the scope of tools represented in the guide.

External Validity: The recruitment of survey participants through professional networks and social media (e.g., LinkedIn) may have introduced a degree of sample bias, particularly in terms of geographic region and professional background. Moreover, the

sample size (n=87) limits the generalizability of the findings. To mitigate these risks, we promoted the survey across different professional communities and validated the content of the questionnaire through a pilot with five practitioners, which helped improve clarity and inclusiveness.

Overall, we recognize these limitations and took proactive steps to minimize their impact. The combination of a multivocal literature review with input from practitioners provides a robust foundation for the development of the practical reference guide.

6 Conclusion

This study combined a Multivocal Literature Review (MLR) and a two-round survey with 87 software practitioners to investigate the usage and perception of test generation tools across academic and industrial contexts. The MLR identified a comprehensive set of tools and their features, while the survey provided empirical evidence of how these tools are perceived, adopted, and evaluated in practice.

Among the tools identified, Postman, Selenium, and Cypress emerged as the most widely recognized and frequently used by practitioners. Participants emphasized features such as visual logs, traceability, and integration with development pipelines as decisive advantages for tool adoption. Conversely, inconsistency of automated tests, high maintenance demands, and dependency on third-party components were reported as the main obstacles to effective adoption and long-term sustainability.

The primary contribution of this work is a Practical Reference Guide that synthesizes the results of the literature review and the practitioner survey to support tool selection decisions. The guide organizes tools by testing domain (API, Mobile, Desktop, Web), test type (functional, regression, load), and licensing model (open-source or commercial), offering a structured view to aid decision-making in software testing projects.

Future work will focus on expanding the study to a larger and more diverse population of professionals, incorporating longitudinal analyses of tool adoption trends, and updating the reference guide to include emerging technologies such as AI-driven test generation. These efforts aim to strengthen the bridge between research and practice and promote the continuous evolution of automated testing tools that effectively meet real-world development needs.

Data Availability

The data underpinning the analysis reported in this paper are deposited on Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/records/17329541>.”

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